

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

On omitted variables, proxies and unobserved effects in empirical regression analysis

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S.I: Statistical regularisation and variable selection

The survey data contains a large number of variables (around 40). But it unknown which of them actually belong to the regression model. In an overfitted model with many variables, estimated coefficients may become implausibly large, while not contributing much to the precision of the model fit. Moreover, the reporting of results is more convenient if irrelevant variables are excluded. We apply the Lasso (least absolute shrinkage and selection operator) as a numerical procedure to eliminate variables that do not or very little contribute to the model. Beside their elimination, the model constraints the sum of the parameters on the regressors, making their interpretation easier. The objective is minimising the usual sum of squared residuals subject to a linear inequality constraint

$$(\hat{\beta}, \hat{\gamma}) \arg \min \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - X_i\beta - W_i\gamma) \text{ subject to } \sum_j \gamma_j \leq \lambda$$

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with λ being the regularisation parameter (Tibshirani, 1996) and W is a regressor set that contains the eventually chosen W_1 but does not include W_2 . The linear inequality constraint leads the Lasso to un-select variables, i.e. $\hat{\gamma}_j = 0$, if their coefficient is small in magnitude. It also leads to the selection of one variable in the case of a group of highly correlated regressors. In order to find $(\hat{\beta}, \hat{\gamma})$ we apply the algorithm suggested by Friedmann et al. (2010). λ is determined by cross-validation such that it minimises the mean squared error. We use the STATA package `elasticregress` (Townsend, 2017). This approach identifies 35 of the W_1 variables to belong to the wage regression. As for the transition model the Lasso does not select any of the variables, we have also applied an Elastic Net which combines the Lasso with a Ridge regression. The Elastic Net did not select additional variables for the transition model.

S.II: Using additional information to test the validity of an instrument in cross sectional analysis

Instrumental variable analysis is popular in applied economic and social sciences research but in order for a candidate for an instrumental variable to be valid it has to pass certain restrictions. In particular, let m be for simplicity one instrumental variable for a component of X , say x_j that is assumed to be endogenous, i.e. $cov(x_j, u) \neq 0$, where u is the error of a regression model, e.g. Model (2). For m being a valid instrument, we need that it is partially correlated with x_j , i.e. playing a role in the reduced form for x_j . This is something one can easily test for. The second requirement is $cov(m, u) = cov(m, W\gamma + v) = cov(m, a + q) = 0$ or $cov(m, b + s + v) = 0$ with a and q as in Model (6) and b, s and v as in Model (7). These conditions cannot easily be tested for in applications, because of unavailability of u, W, a and b . By exploiting the availability of W_1 and the panel dimension of the data as outlined in Section 2, we suggest the following tests for instrument validity. Once $W_1\gamma_1, a$ and b are (consistently) estimated, one can use them to empirically check if m is partially correlated with $W_1\hat{\gamma}_1, \hat{a}$ or \hat{b} . Any non zero covariance would point to endogeneity of m . Even including Z and or W_1 in the model will not render m exogenous if time-constant unobservables are correlated with FEs.

We apply this to the data of the transition analysis. As candidate for an instrumental variable we use the regional treatment intensity as it has been used for similar empirical research (Frölich and Lechner, 2010; Bookmann et al., 2014). This is the share of unemployed job seekers that has been assigned into a treatment measure by an employment agency district. Similar variables have been used to address possible endogeneity of the individual level variable "participation in an active labour market policy program in the past 3 years" (or subsequently denoted as z_j) that is of high policy relevance. Table S2 reports the resulting covariances and pairwise

Table S2: Transition Analysis: Testing for endogeneity

	$Cov(\hat{b}, \cdot)$	$\rho_{\hat{b}, \cdot}$
Regional treatment intensity	-0.0106	-0.0522**
Participation in active labour market programmes in the past 3 years	0.064038	0.0738***

ρ : pairwise correlation

* $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.010$

correlations between estimated FEs \hat{b} , and the candidate instrument m and the regressor z_j , respectively. We do not consider $W_1 \hat{\gamma}_{(1)}$ as there is no W_1 in this model and we do not consider \hat{a} as the endogeneous regressor is an element of Z . It is apparent that the relationships are rather weak but not strictly zero. The correlation of m with \hat{b} is -0.05 with a p-value of 0.04. There is therefore some evidence for the instrument not being valid. It is an empirical question whether a two stage least squares (2SLS) estimator has a smaller or larger bias than an OLS estimator. But given that $\rho_{\hat{b}, z_j}$ is only marginally larger in magnitude than $\rho_{\hat{b}, m}$, the instrument needs to be strong to make the IV estimator less biased and sufficiently precise in the application.

S.III: Transition Analysis

In this supplement we repeat the analysis of the wage analysis by considering a probability model for leaving unemployment. In the transition analysis, we consider 1,484 individuals once registered as unemployed during the interview year, observed for at least three years in the administrative data. In particular, the dependent variable (y) indicates whether an unemployed individual left unemployment within 12 months ($y = 1$) or not ($y = 0$) since the time of the interview. We apply the linear probability model to estimate the partial relationship between various observables and the transition probability. In the transition analysis, variables include past unemployment history at the transition time, current unemployment episode duration, recall history, past long-term unemployment, and participation in active labor market programs within the past three years. While Z may belong to the population model, they are endogenous due to their correlation with unobservable factors, necessitating the addition of W_1 variables to uncover endogeneity.

As this analysis is restricted to unemployed job seekers, the sample conditions on those being in the job seekers register. For this reason, firm level variables are no longer available but other variables such as claiming unemployment benefits. The full set of variables is again provided in Table S6 in supplement S.IV. Also, the set of work history variable Z changes and becomes related to past unemployment experiences and participation in active labour market policy programs. As mentioned above, none of the survey variables have been selected by the Lasso and elastic net, thus the set W_1 is empty. This suggests that the survey does not contribute relevant information to the analysis.

Table S3: Transition analysis: Binary dependent variable (Dummy: left unemployment within 12 months)

	T.A $E(y X)$ coef. / (SE)	T.B $E(y X, Z)$ coef. / (SE)	T.C $E(y_{it} X_{it})$ coef. / (SE)	T.D $E(y_{it} X_{it}, Z_{it})$ coef. / (SE)
Gender (male=1)	0.043* (0.022)	0.034 (0.021)	0.111 (0.879)	-0.833 (0.966)
Age	-0.003*** (0.001)	-0.002* (0.001)	0.016 (0.023)	0.033 (0.026)
Missing information on education	-0.007 (0.104)	0.006 (0.099)	0.048 (0.183)	0.013 (0.143)
No formal degree	-0.010 (0.095)	-0.030 (0.090)	-0.003 (0.172)	-0.033 (0.133)
Vocational training	0.025 (0.094)	0.005 (0.089)	0.030 (0.168)	-0.003 (0.127)
Higher Education	0.043 (0.128)	-0.021 (0.127)	0.094 (0.186)	0.053 (0.151)
Dummy: German nationality	0.002 (0.037)	0.003 (0.034)	-0.077 (0.074)	-0.058 (0.068)

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... table S3 continued

	T.A	T.B	T.C	T.D
	coef. / (SE)	coef. / (SE)	coef. / (SE)	coef. / (SE)
Dummy: receiving unemployment insurance benefits	0.121*** (0.026)	0.034 (0.025)	0.322*** (0.097)	0.201*** (0.073)
Dummy: receiving mean-tested unemployment benefits	-0.163*** (0.031)	-0.088** (0.036)	0.003 (0.144)	0.092 (0.121)
Dummy: West Germany	-0.006 (0.023)	-0.023 (0.023)	0.027 (0.097)	0.024 (0.095)
Dummy: left unemployment in the past		0.510*** (0.044)		0.537*** (0.063)
Unemployment duration (in months)		-0.003*** (0.000)		-0.020*** (0.002)
Dummy: left long-term unemployment (>12 months) in the past		-0.009 (0.032)		0.293*** (0.043)
Dummy: be recalled in the past		0.022 (0.025)		-0.004 (0.039)
Dummy: participation in active labour market programmes in the past 3 years		0.035 (0.022)		-0.000 (0.026)
Constant	0.949*** (0.119)	0.555*** (0.118)		
N	1484	1484	3×1484	3×1484
R ²	0.036	0.151	0.925	0.936
Percent correctly predicted (PCP)	0.763	0.787		

Robust standard errors in parentheses. Heteroskedasticity-robust tests.

* p<0.10, ** p<0.05, *** p<0.010

Table S3 shows the estimation results for the models $P(y = 1|X)$, $P(y = 1|X, Z)$, $P(y_{it} = 1|X_{it})$ and $P(y_{it} = 1|X_{it}, Z_{it})$, which are denoted as T.A - T.D, respectively. It is apparent that the estimated coefficients on the X variables are often similar and statistically not different across the regressions T.A and T.B, except for the benefit claim related variables, which both decrease in magnitude. The R^2 increases from 0.036 to 0.151, which shows that the work history variables contribute to the model, though, the Percent Correctly Predicted (PCP) only very marginally increases from 0.763 to 0.787 due to the inclusion of Z . The results for the panel models T.C and T.D in Table S3 show also only evidence for a small number of coefficients (X, Z) to be sizably different in comparison to Models T.A and T.B. The coefficient on receiving unemployment insurance benefits increases considerably, while the coefficient on receiving mean-tested unemployment benefits changes sign but loses statistical significance. Among the Z variables, only the coefficients on unemployment duration and on having left long-term unemployment change. In particular, they increase strongly in magnitude in Model T.D. As the latter is the interaction of having been long term unemployed and having left unemployment in the past, these results suggest that past successes play an important role in explaining future successes. While the W_1 variables turned out to be irrelevant, the Z variables

appear to be the most important variables in the transition model and they remain relevant after controlling for unobserved FEs. Thus, they may be relevant in the population model or may be related to time-varying information in W_2 that has not been captured by the panel models.

Table S4: Transition sample: Regression based endogeneity test for components of X and Z

	(1)	(2)
	$E(a X)$	$E(b X, Z)$
	$\beta / (SE)$	$\beta / (SE)$
Gender (male=1)	-2.844*** (0.018)	-2.020*** (0.018)
Age	0.151*** (0.001)	0.110*** (0.001)
Missing information on education	-0.024 (0.073)	0.024 (0.077)
No formal degree	-0.005 (0.067)	-0.013 (0.070)
Vocational training	0.008 (0.066)	0.014 (0.069)
Higher Education	-0.027 (0.098)	-0.032 (0.097)
Dummy: German nationality	0.054* (0.030)	0.051* (0.027)
Dummy: receiving unemployment insurance benefits	-0.232*** (0.021)	-0.196*** (0.020)
Dummy: receiving mean-tested unemployment benefits	-0.117*** (0.028)	-0.117*** (0.034)
Dummy: West Germany	-0.062*** (0.019)	-0.077*** (0.019)
Dummy: left unemployment in the past		0.040 (0.039)
Unemployment duration (in months)		0.017*** (0.000)
Dummy: left long-term unemployment (>12 months) in the past		-0.274*** (0.026)
Dummy: be recalled in the past		0.031 (0.020)
Dummy: participation in active labour market programmes in the past 3 years		0.041** (0.017)
Constant	0.953*** (0.089)	0.565*** (0.096)
N	1484	1484
R^2	0.976	0.968

Robust standard errors in parentheses. Heteroskedasticity-robust tests.

* $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.010$

Table S4 presents the results for the linear projection of X and X, Z on the estimated FEs.

Similar to the wage regressions, there is evidence of endogeneity of a number of variables in the cross sectional Models T.A and T.B. However, as already elaborated, our results suggest that the omitted variable bias is limited for most variables in the transition model. Table S4 also shows that the included regressors almost perfectly explain the variation in estimated FEs, which suggests again a multicollinearity pattern for a subset of the regressors in Table S3.

Before finishing this application we pay some special focus on the variable "participation in an active labour market policy program" as participation in an active labour market policy program, such as training, is a policy relevant variable that has received a lot of attention in empirical labour market research. We do not find economically, nor statistically relevant changes when comparing Models T.B and T.D. Our findings confirm the findings of Lechner and Wunsch (2013) and Caliendo et al. (2014), who focus on estimation of treatments effects on labour market transitions. By sets of operations based administrative or interview based survey variables to their models, they find that the estimated treatment effects are stable and thus may not be affected by omitted variables. Despite the observed coefficient stability, our endogeneity tests in Table S4 provide some evidence of endogeneity of the treatment variable. A popular approach to tackle endogeneity of labour market treatment variables is to use instrumental variable techniques (e.g. Frölich and Lechner, 2010; Bookmann et al., 2014). We follow this route and construct the regional treatment intensity as a candidate for an instrumental variable. In supplement S.II we outline how the models of Section 2 can be used to test for validity of candidates for instrumental variables. When applying this to the transition sample we find some evidence for the instrument to be correlated with unobserved model components, although the estimated correlations are small (around 0.05 in magnitude). Despite that there is some evidence of instrument invalidity, it is an empirical question whether an IV procedure is more or less biased than an OLS estimate and will also depend on the instrument strength. It is remarked that instrument endogeneity can arise through correlation with omitted model components despite that the instrument is not a direct component of the population model and not related to other observable regressors.

S.IV: Tables

Table S5: Variable selection by LASSO and elastic net

Variable Names
<i>Wage sample:</i>
Big Five: I am rather cautious, reserved
Big Five: I tend to criticise people
Big Five: I attend to all my assignments with precision
Big Five: I have versatile interests
Big Five: I am inspirable and can inspire other people
Big Five: I easily trust in people and believe in the good in humans
Big Five: I tend to be lazy
Big Five: I am profound and like to think about things
Big Five: I am rather quiet, introverted
Big Five: I can act cold and distant
Big Five: I am industrious and work hard
Big Five: I worry a lot
Big Five: I have a vivid imagination and have a lot of phantasy
Big Five: I am outgoing and like company
Big Five: I can be gruff and repellend towards other people
Big Five: I make plans and carry them out
Big Five: I easily get nervous and insecure
Big Five: I treasure artistic and aesthetic impressions
Big Five: I am not very interested in art
Dummy: satisfied with one?s life in general
Dummy: was looking for a new job
Dummy: was looking for an additional job
Dummy: was looking for a new and an additional job
strength of connection to place of residence
Frequency of misunderstandings, tensions or conflicts
Number of children in total (within and outside the household)
Number of children in household
Dummy: none of parents has a HE degree
Dummy: one parent has a HE degree
Current contract working time,total, without mini-job
Current actual working time, main occupation, without mini-job

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... table S5 continued

Variable Names

Current actual working time,total, without mini-job

Dummy: none of parents with migrational background

Size of household

Not Selected by LASSO:

Big Five: I tend to be depressed, crestfallen

Big Five: I am relaxed and don't let stress get to me

Dummy: satisfied with health

Working even without being dependent on wage

Number of real close friends/family members outside the household

Transition sample:

No variable is selected by LASSO and elastic net

Table S6: Descriptive statistics

Variable Names	Wage				Transition			
	mean	sd	min	max	mean	sd	min	max
<i>y variables:</i>								
log(average daily gross wage)	4.15	0.66	1.21	5.44	-	-	-	-
Dummy: left unemployment within 12 months	-	-	-	-	0.76	0.42	0.00	1.00
<i>X variables:</i>								
Gender (male=1)	0.47	0.50	0.00	1.00	0.40	0.49	0.00	1.00
Age	42.87	10.19	18.00	64.00	39.74	11.30	17.00	63.00
Dummy: trainee	0.00	0.04	0.00	1.00	-	-	-	-
Missing information on education	0.00	0.07	0.00	1.00	0.06	0.25	0.00	1.00
No formal degree	0.12	0.33	0.00	1.00	0.31	0.46	0.00	1.00
Vocational training	0.75	0.43	0.00	1.00	0.60	0.49	0.00	1.00
Higher Education	0.11	0.31	0.00	1.00	0.01	0.12	0.00	1.00
Dummy: German nationality	0.96	0.19	0.00	1.00	0.89	0.32	0.00	1.00
Dummy: West Germany	-	-	-	-	0.63	0.48	0.00	1.00
Agriculture	0.01	0.09	0.00	1.00	-	-	-	-
Hotel and restaurant	0.03	0.18	0.00	1.00	-	-	-	-
Construction	0.05	0.22	0.00	1.00	-	-	-	-
Trade	0.14	0.35	0.00	1.00	-	-	-	-
Services	0.29	0.45	0.00	1.00	-	-	-	-
Education and social health	0.20	0.40	0.00	1.00	-	-	-	-
Public institutions	0.07	0.25	0.00	1.00	-	-	-	-
Other sectors	0.02	0.14	0.00	1.00	-	-	-	-
Dummy: receiving unemployment insurance benefits	-	-	-	-	0.67	0.47	0.00	1.00
Dummy: receiving mean-tested unemployment assistance	-	-	-	-	0.37	0.48	0.00	1.00
<i>Z variables:</i>								
Tenure (in years)	4.85	5.99	0.00	36.59	-	-	-	-
Share of working experience over total observation time	0.53	0.34	0.00	1.00	-	-	-	-
Additional working experience (in years)	8.31	8.03	0.00	36.14	-	-	-	-
Dummy: unemployment history in the past	0.74	0.44	0.00	1.00	-	-	-	-
Dummy: left unemployment in the past	-	-	-	-	0.89	0.31	0.00	1.00
Unemployment duration (in months)	-	-	-	-	40.19	30.20	0.00	133.13
Dummy: left long-term unemployment(>12 months) in the past	-	-	-	-	0.22	0.41	0.00	1.00
Dummy: be recalled in the past	-	-	-	-	0.73	0.44	0.00	1.00
Dummy: participation in an active labour market policy program in the past 3 years	-	-	-	-	0.39	0.49	0.00	1.00
<i>W1 variables:</i>								
Big Five: I am rather cautious, reserved	2.82	1.16	1.00	5.00	-	-	-	-
Big Five: I tend to criticise people	2.73	1.12	1.00	5.00	-	-	-	-
Big Five: I attend to all my assignments with precision	4.41	0.71	1.00	5.00	-	-	-	-
Big Five: I have versatile interests	4.22	0.83	1.00	5.00	-	-	-	-
Big Five: I am inspirable and can inspire other people	3.80	1.02	1.00	5.00	-	-	-	-

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... table S6 continued

Variable Names	Wage				Transition			
	mean	sd	min	max	mean	sd	min	max
Big Five: I easily trust in people and believe in the good in humans	3.57	1.12	1.00	5.00	-	-	-	-
Big Five: I tend to be lazy	2.21	1.10	1.00	5.00	-	-	-	-
Big Five: I am profound and like to think about things	3.70	1.05	1.00	5.00	-	-	-	-
Big Five: I am rather quiet, introverted	2.52	1.21	1.00	5.00	-	-	-	-
Big Five: I can act cold and distant	3.10	1.24	1.00	5.00	-	-	-	-
Big Five: I am industrious and work hard	4.31	0.65	1.00	5.00	-	-	-	-
Big Five: I worry a lot	3.23	1.18	1.00	5.00	-	-	-	-
Big Five: I have a vivid imagination and have a lot of phantasy	3.81	0.96	1.00	5.00	-	-	-	-
Big Five: I am outgoing and like company	3.71	1.01	1.00	5.00	-	-	-	-
Big Five: I can be gruff and repellend towards other people	3.01	1.18	1.00	5.00	-	-	-	-
Big Five: I make plans and carry them out	3.98	0.85	1.00	5.00	-	-	-	-
Big Five: I easily get nervous and insecure	2.43	1.03	1.00	5.00	-	-	-	-
Big Five: I treasure artistic and aesthetic impressions	3.34	1.19	1.00	5.00	-	-	-	-
Big Five: I am not very interested in art	2.76	1.26	1.00	5.00	-	-	-	-
Dummy: satisfied with one's life in general	0.88	0.32	0.00	1.00	-	-	-	-
Dummy: was looking for a new job	0.08	0.27	0.00	1.00	-	-	-	-
Dummy: was looking for an additional job	0.01	0.12	0.00	1.00	-	-	-	-
Dummy: was not looking for a new job	0.91	0.29	0.00	1.00	-	-	-	-
Dummy: was looking for a new and an additional job	0.00	0.05	0.00	1.00	-	-	-	-
strength of connection to place of residence	1.98	0.96	1.00	5.00	-	-	-	-
Frequency of misunderstandings, tensions or conflicts	3.55	0.95	1.00	5.00	-	-	-	-
Number of children in total (within and outside the household)	1.53	1.13	0.00	7.00	-	-	-	-
Number of children in household	1.07	1.02	0.00	7.00	-	-	-	-
Dummy: none of parents has a HE degree	0.53	0.50	0.00	1.00	-	-	-	-
Dummy: one parent has a HE degree	0.08	0.27	0.00	1.00	-	-	-	-
Current contract working time,total, without mini-job	33.83	9.17	0.00	80.00	-	-	-	-
Current actual working time, main occupation, without mini-job	37.49	11.37	0.00	80.00	-	-	-	-
Current actual working time,total, without mini-job	37.85	11.87	0.00	120.00	-	-	-	-
Dummy: none of parents with migrational background	0.06	0.24	0.00	1.00	-	-	-	-
Size of household	3.11	1.09	2.00	10.00	-	-	-	-

Table S7: Estimated coefficients on W_1 variables in Models W.C and W.D
(continued from Table 2)

	$E(y X, W_1)$ coef. / (SE)	$E(y X, Z, W_1)$ coef. / (SE)
Big Five: I am rather cautious, reserved	-0.017 (0.011)	-0.017* (0.010)
Big Five: I tend to criticise people	0.025** (0.010)	0.026*** (0.009)
Big Five: I attend to all my assignments with precision	-0.019 (0.014)	-0.016 (0.013)
Big Five: I have versatile interests	0.001 (0.013)	0.006 (0.012)
Big Five: I am inspirable and can inspire other people	-0.009 (0.011)	-0.009 (0.011)
Big Five: I easily trust in people and believe in the good in humans	0.002 (0.009)	0.007 (0.008)
Big Five: I tend to be lazy	0.036*** (0.010)	0.036*** (0.009)
Big Five: I am profound and like to think about things	0.018* (0.010)	0.018* (0.009)
Big Five: I am rather quiet, introverted	-0.009 (0.010)	-0.010 (0.009)
Big Five: I can act cold and distant	-0.005 (0.008)	-0.005 (0.008)
Big Five: I am industrious and work hard	-0.008 (0.018)	-0.002 (0.017)
Big Five: I worry a lot	-0.023** (0.009)	-0.018** (0.009)
Big Five: I have a vivid imagination and have a lot of phantasy	0.004 (0.011)	-0.000 (0.010)
Big Five: I am outgoing and like company	-0.028** (0.011)	-0.029*** (0.010)
Big Five: I can be gruff and repellend towards other people	-0.007 (0.010)	-0.000 (0.009)
Big Five: I make plans and carry them out	0.059*** (0.013)	0.050*** (0.012)
Big Five: I easily get nervous and insecure	-0.023** (0.011)	-0.019* (0.011)
Big Five: I treasure artistic and aesthetic impressions	0.005 (0.010)	0.009 (0.009)
Big Five: I am not very interested in art	0.000 (0.010)	-0.004 (0.009)
Dummy: satisfied with one?s life in general	0.164*** (0.031)	0.122*** (0.029)
Dummy: was looking for a new job	-0.180*** (0.035)	-0.128*** (0.033)
Dummy: was looking for an additional job	-0.028 (0.087)	-0.001 (0.079)
Dummy: was looking for a new and an additional job	-0.093 (0.171)	-0.030 (0.179)

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	$E(y X, W1)$ coef. / (SE)	$E(y X, Z, W1)$ coef. / (SE)
strength of connection to place of residence	0.017* (0.010)	0.024*** (0.009)
Frequency of misunderstandings, tensions or conflicts	-0.024** (0.011)	-0.023** (0.011)
Number of children in total (within and outside the household)	-0.060*** (0.014)	-0.027** (0.013)
Number of children in household	0.050*** (0.017)	0.049*** (0.017)
Dummy: none of parents has a HE degree	0.033 (0.020)	0.013 (0.019)
Dummy: one parent has a HE degree	0.105*** (0.036)	0.100*** (0.034)
Current contract working time, total, without mini-job	0.021*** (0.002)	0.020*** (0.002)
Current actual working time, main occupation, without mini-job	0.022*** (0.003)	0.020*** (0.003)
Current actual working time, total, without mini-job	-0.011*** (0.004)	-0.010*** (0.003)
Dummy: none of parents with migrational background	0.089** (0.040)	0.108*** (0.039)
Size of household	0.011 (0.013)	-0.015 (0.013)
N	2435	2435
R^2	0.502	0.570

* p<0.10, ** p<0.05, *** p<0.010

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